

EELS probing of lithium based 2-D battery compounds processed by liquid phase exfoliation

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Abstract

Two-dimensional lithiated nanosheets usually show excellent electrochemical performance due to an increase in surface area and shorter diffusion paths. However, processing techniques, such as shear mixing or liquid phase exfoliation could induce phase changes or knock out some of the structural lithium (Li) ions, what in turn might result in poor electrochemical performance. Here different lithiated layered compounds mainly LiCoO_2 , LiMn_2O_4 , and $\text{Li}_5\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$ were chemically exfoliated and investigated using electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) for their Li-K edge. Further analyses were carried out, looking at the oxygen (O) K edge with their respective transition metal core loss peak (Mn, Co and Ti) which revealed changes in the Energy loss near edge structures (ELNES) when compared to the unlithiated compounds. STEM-EELS analyses confirmed uneven distribution of lithium within the lithiated layered materials. In this work, EELS was used for the first time to detect and to probe the chemical environment of the lithium in liquid phase exfoliated material.

1. Introduction

Nanomaterials hold great potential as electrode materials in rechargeable batteries, as they increase the available surface area, reduce the diffusion distances and maximize the electrochemical utilization of the active material. Therefore, it is not surprising that several synthesis techniques have been used to produce these nanomaterials, such as chemical precipitation followed by thermal annealing [30], sol-gel [31] and molten salt decomposition [32]. However, these methods are not easily transferred from the laboratory to industrial scale applications. Moreover, they encompass several steps and end up being time consuming approaches. In recent years a thorough study of two-dimensional materials and the need for an easily scalable and cheaper technique, led to development of liquid phase exfoliation [2]. Liquid exfoliation of bulk material is one of the most efficient means of producing 2-D materials in a large-scale quantities [2] and it has been widely used for the production of nanosheets of graphene [34,6], MnO₂ [33], boron nitride [2], among other materials [2,3,10]. In theory, all materials can be exfoliated in a liquid phase as long as they are layered crystals composed by sheets of covalently bonded atoms, kept together by weak van der Waals forces. This is in fact the case of LiCoO₂ which is the most popular active material for lithium ion batteries. Therefore, it is almost certain that 2D LiCoO₂ can be obtained by liquid phase exfoliation. However, it is not yet fully clear how the exfoliation process affects electronic and crystal structure or stability of the exfoliated materials. Moreover, the extreme processing conditions might knock out some light lithium atoms, and therefore the obtained flakes might present different chemical/structural compositions. Greater understanding of these effects is necessary in order to fully exploit the material's potential. In order to do so, proper characterization tools and techniques should be sought and developed. Nevertheless, a detailed study of light elements can be a cumbersome task. XPS and synchrotron XRD [35] are powerful tools that can easily detect lithium. However, these techniques lack the required spatial resolution to study lithium distribution across a single layered material. Recent reports, suggest that Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) could be used instead, as it allows the detection of light elements while maintaining the high spatial resolution of the electron microscope [18,29]. Moreover, the Li K-edge and other core loss regions, including the O K-edge, provide vital information on the lithium's electronic environment. In particular, the question of whether the lithium remains in the expected coordination state in the structures under investigation or whether it has already been knocked out from the lattice planes can be addressed using this information. Even, when compared with other microscopy techniques, EELS presents advantages, such as a low dose rate (parallel beam as compared to convergent beam in STEM). This property is in fact very important. For instance, the Atomic Sensitivity Factor

(ASF) of lithium is approximately one hundred times lower than that of manganese (0.02 for the Li 1s state compared with 1.7 for the Mn 2p_{3/2} state [13]). Therefore, using electron diffraction, it is difficult to differentiate between elastic scattering events due to the presence of lithium or those resulting from changes in the structure due to beam damage. In fact, the nature of these materials means that they are more vulnerable to beam damage [23]. A recent study by Wang *et al.* [11] showed that a 60 KeV electron beam causes more damage to lithium than a beam at 300 KeV. This behaviour may be due to the small lithium nucleus and the fact that the elastic electron-lithium scattering cross section is larger at lower energies [14]. Moreover, the low atomic number of Li results in a weak electron scattering, what in turn makes detection and analysis extremely challenging, particularly in exfoliated layered compounds due to the decreased stability of the exfoliated material when compared to its bulk counterpart, which is currently more commonly used in the design of electrodes.

In this work, we report for the first time the physico-chemical characterization of 2D nanosheets of LiCoO₂, prepared by liquid phase exfoliation in IPA. As EELS relies in the inelastic cross-section and not on the atomic number Z, it is used in TEM/STEM mode to identify light elements in the as-prepared exfoliated materials. Further core loss spectra analyses has been undertaken to probe the chemical environment of the system and hence prove the lithium bonding in the 2-D flakes even after undergoing chemical exfoliation. To further extend this analysis to other lithiated compounds, dispersions of Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ in water and LiMn₂O₄ in IPA were also prepared by liquid phase exfoliation and analyzed by EELS. These materials are not the typical layered crystals described elsewhere [2]. However, through this work we will use the term “exfoliation” for the synthesis of 2D nanomaterials by sonication and further stabilization according to the solubility parameters theory [28].

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Characterization of the raw lithiated materials

In Fig. 1.a-c are shown SEM micrographs of LiCoO₂, LiMn₂O₄ and Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ before the exfoliation process. According to these micrographs all of the materials present particles with dimensions in the micrometer range. Contrary to LiMn₂O₄ and Li₄Ti₅O₁₂, LiCoO₂ particles do not present a regular shape, however its layered structure can be clearly seen. In order to determine the crystal structure of these lithiated materials, X-ray diffraction was performed in the samples under study. The XRD spectra in Fig. 1.d reveal sharp narrow peaks for all the samples, indicating that these materials are highly crystalline.

Figure 1- SEM micrographs of (a) LiCoO_2 , (b) LiMn_2O_4 and (c) $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ powders and (d) their respective XRD spectra.

Moreover, as no additional phases were detected, it is possible to suggest as well that the samples are very pure. In a more detailed way, from Rietveld analysis it results that the lattice parameters of LiCoO_2 are $a=2.81498 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=14.04930 \text{ \AA}$ (JCPDS card no. 75-0532). According to the literature, these values correspond to a layered $\alpha\text{-NaFeO}_2$ type structure (hexagonal, R-3m, space group 166) [15]. LiCoO_2 can also crystallize in a spinel-like form (cubic, Fd-3m), which present an XRD pattern quite similar to the previously mentioned layered structure. However, no evidence of this phase could be found [1]. For LiMn_2O_4 the XRD pattern indicates a spinel type of structure (cubic, Fd-3m, space group 227) with $a=8.24762 \text{ \AA}$ (JCPDS card no.35- 0782) [16]. Finally, for $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ a value of $a=8.35880 \text{ \AA}$ was obtained (JCPDS card no. 26-1198), also corresponding to spinel (cubic, Fd-3m, space group 227) [17]. The data obtained from XRD spectra is in good agreement with previously published reports, suggesting once again the purity and high quality of the used materials. After the initial characterization, LiCoO_2 , LiMn_2O_4 and $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ flakes were produced by liquid phase exfoliation. Detailed information on this process can be found in the ESI.

2.2. EEL spectroscopic analyses

The Li-K edge of lithiated compounds namely LiCoO_2 , LiMn_2O_4 and $\text{Li}_5\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$ has been shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 - The EELS signals of all the materials examined showing the presence lithium (red arrows). Other reference spectra of MnO₂, cobalt oxide and titanium oxide (comparing with the lithiated ones) is given in Supporting information (refer Fig. S8).

Fig. 3a shows a micrograph of a typical 2D flake of LiCoO₂ prepared by a liquid phase exfoliation method in IPA. The presence of lithium and its distribution on such flakes was studied by TEM-EELS. Due to plasmon background intensity and interband transitions, the Li K-edge is difficult to detect (due to its higher knock on probability and smaller scattering power). Moreover, it is also strongly dependent on the Li content [18,12]. If the angle of scattering is small, since the dipole selection rule is satisfied, the intensities of the Li and O K-edges are proportional to the unoccupied 'Li' and 'O' partial density of states (PDOS) respectively, (since the dipole selection rule is satisfied) [19,20]. In the case of LiCoO₂ the M_{2,3}-edge of cobalt is at an electron energy loss of 60 eV and the lithium K-edge (in pristine state) is located at 55 eV. While these two edges are located very close to one another, they are easily distinguishable due to their different shapes. Lithium's K-edge has an abrupt onset, while cobalt's M_{2,3}-edge is present at a slightly higher energy and has a delayed maximum. Experimentally measured lithium K-edges observed in a number of lithium compounds can be found in Wang *et al.* [11]. In the present work, TEM-EELS spectra collected using a broad beam spread across the entire flakes allowed the detection of lithium. The inhomogeneity of the flakes suggests that the lithium concentration is likely to vary across flakes. Moreover, the distribution of this element depends on the thickness of the flake with more lithium likely to remain in thicker regions. Fig. 3b shows TEM-EELS spectra collected with the electron beam focused onto an area of Fig. 2. The EELS signals of all the materials examined showing the presence lithium (red arrows). Other reference

spectra of MnO₂, cobalt oxide and titanium oxide (comparing with the lithiated ones) is given in Supporting information (refer Fig. S8).

Figure 3 - (a) Bright field TEM image of a flake of LiCoO₂. The TEM beam was condensed to a diameter of approximately 10 nm and EELS spectra were collected from regions marked A and B. (b) EELS spectra collected from the regions marked A and B in (a). The lithium signal is clearly present in the spectrum collected from the centre of the flake, while it is absent from the spectrum collected from the edge. (c) The percentage of flakes in which a lithium signal was detected for each centrifugation speed. (e) The EELS spectrum collected from a LiCoO₂ flake (d) as the flake remains illuminated by the beam over a period of four minutes. The lithium signal is clearly visible in the first spectrum and decreases over time until it is completely absent.

Prolong exposure to electron beam knocks out the lithium as shown in Fig. 3(e). Similar results were obtained for LiMn₂O₄ wherein after 0.9×10^4 C/cm² electron dose, there was no Li signal (Fig. S9 Supporting information). The presence of lithium in the thicker region of the flake and its absence in the thinner region suggests that the lithium was more likely to be removed from flakes that have been more efficiently exfoliated (Although we made sure to keep the e-dose low, we cannot discard the fact that the lithium in the thinner regions might be present but knocked out quickly due to beam and hence undetectable). In order to further investigate the possibility that lithium was more fully removed from LiCoO₂ flakes that had been more efficiently exfoliated, different batches of flakes were prepared in which the centrifugation speed was set to 500 rpm, 3,000 rpm and 5,000 rpm. Each of these spectra was examined for the presence of lithium and cobalt. For each centrifugation speed the number of flakes in which both lithium and cobalt present were detected. Fig. 3c shows how the percentage of flakes in which lithium was detected, decreases with increased

centrifugation speed. Proving that the lithium content varies with thickness of the material within the same flake.

The thickness of the flakes cannot be determined precisely using conventional techniques. However, qualitatively it can be estimated that the flakes centrifuged at 500 rpm are 10 times thicker than those centrifuged at 5000 rpm (this was known by looking at the intensity of the EFTE image). Further details are in the Supplementary information, Fig. S5.

All the flakes were centrifuged at 1500 rpm. Fig. 3d shows the EEL spectra collected when a LiCoO_2 flake was illuminated by an electron beam of approximately 300 nm in diameter, with a screen current of 10.6 nA. Each spectra were collected every 30 s over a period of four minutes. The Li K-edge is clearly visible at time $t=0$. However, it becomes less apparent in each subsequent spectrum and it is completely absent from the spectrum collected after two minutes under the electron beam exposure (Fig. 3e). There was no apparent change in the Co $M_{2,3}$ -edge signal. These changes in lithium signal are in good agreement with report published by Kikkawa *et al.* (on examination of the TEM-EELS spectra for Li_xCoO_2 ($x < 1$), for varying values of x [18]).

So far the low loss EELS studies demonstrate the presence of lithium, however, given the energy resolution it is not possible to determine whether or not the lithium remains bonded to the transition metals. Moreover, the quantification of the Li concentration is not reliable due to difficulty in the subtraction of background plasmon peaks. As the sample been subjected to a chemical exfoliation process, lithium that is being detected might be the one which has been already removed from the layered crystal. If this is the case, the oxidation and the chemical state of the transition metal and the O K-edge peak would not be affected when you compare the lithiated and unlithiated compound.

In order to test this hypothesis, in depth analyses of the core loss spectra is shown in Fig. 4a and b of O K- and Co L_3 -edges [38]. Transitions from 1s to empty 2p orbitals and from $2p_{3/2}$ to empty 3d orbitals respectively, for LiCoO_2 , centrifuged at 500 and 5000 rpm. The O K-edge and Co L_3 -edge show a peak broadening in the 5000 rpm sample where the Li-K edge was absent (lithium was found to be present only in 40%–45% of the observed flakes) indicated by the blue arrow in Fig. 4b. The O K-edge also displays a shift of 0.8 eV towards lower energies. Its fine structure shows a minute peak (blue arrow in Fig. 4a), which is typical for CoO/ CoO_2 material [21]. This is not visible for the lithiated electron energy-loss near edge structure (ELNES) of the O K-edge. This broadening could be explained via the change in the PDOS for empty Co 3d and O 2p orbitals.

Figure 4 - (a, b) shows O K-edge and Co L-edge of LiCo_2O_4 respectively. (c,d) Li-K edge and Ti-L/O-K edge respectively for $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$, (e and f) O-K edge and Mn-L edge respectively of LiMn_2O_4 .

Changes in the ELNES structure can be attributed to the band formed below original Co e_g band, which is a hybridized state of O 2p and Co $a_{1g}-e_g$ [18]. This illustrates charge transfer from lithium indicating lithium bonding towards CoO. Work done by Won-Sub Yoon *et al.* [22] using XPS had observed similar patterns of broadening of the O K-edge peak as lithium ion deintercalation occurs.

In order to extend this analyses to other materials, flakes of $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and LiMn_2O_4 were prepared by liquid phase exfoliation as well, were examined using the same TEM-EELS approach (the acquired EELS spectra were compared with TiO_2 and Mn_2O_4 flakes, respectively).

Fig. 4d shows the Ti $L_{2,3}$ -edge, which represents a transition from $2p^6 3d^n$ to $2p^5 3d^{n+1}$, for the EELS spectra collected from $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and TiO_2 . The spectra were aligned at the Ti L_3 -edge so that the O K-edge chemical shift could be measured, this was found to be of the order 1.6 eV towards higher energies for the lithiated compound. Examination of the $L_{2,3}$ -edge reveals crystal field splitting for TiO_2 , though the 3d orbital of $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ doesn't show any doublets. The O K-edge peak (shown by dotted lines) shows the electron transition from the oxygen 1s to 2p states, which is in turn hybridized with Ti 4s and 4p states. This suggests charge transfer from Li to Ti ions [4].

In Fig. 4e and f are shown the O K-edge and the Mn $L_{2,3}$ -edges, for LiMn_2O_4 and MnO_2 respectively. A peak shift of 2.6 eV towards higher energies is observed in LiMn_2O_4 . This is due to the (+4) Mn oxidation state in LiMn_2O_4 [25]. Unlike in other transition metal significant conclusions could not be drawn from the structure of the Mn 2p peak of MnO_2 and LiMn_2O_4 shown in Fig. 4e as the coupling of angular momenta of partially filled core and valence shells having unpaired electrons results in multiple splitting of the peak [24,36,37]. Similar studies done by Ramana *et al.* [25] did not report any change in the oxygen 1s core level and suggests that there is no change in O K-edge upon lithium substitution. However, a prominent difference is observed in the fine structure of the O K-edge for LiMn_2O_4 and MnO_2 spectra marked a, b and c. Also, after aligning the Mn 2p peak shift, the fine structure of the O K-edge of the lithiated spectrum shifted 1.2 eV to higher binding energies. Whereas in other study done by Kumagai *et al.* [26] a shoulder at higher binding energies with respect to the main O K-edge was observed without any shift in the main peak after an increase in Li intercalation. Analysis of the O K-edge reveals a variation in the fine structure. This could be due to the nature of the sample further investigation of this is necessary. The XPS of LiMn_2O_4 , when compared to the MnO , displays additional shoulders at the Mn 3p and Mn 2p peaks at 49 eV and 642 eV, respectively. The broadening of the peak indicates a change in the number of chemical bonds (further discussion and XPS spectra included in the ESI).

2.3. Delocalized STEM

In TEM mode, there is less control over the beam position when it comes to small flakes. Therefore tracking the distribution of lithium across a flake is an extreme challenge in STEM

mode as significant knock-on damage (due to sample being 2-D layered structure and hence more sensitive to beam damage) results in no Li signal (ESI, Fig:S12). This could be overcome by increasing the beam diameter in STEM mode; however, this results in a highly compromised spatial resolution.

Figure 5. HAADF STEM image of a LiCoO₂ flake. Brighter regions of the image correspond to thicker regions of the flake (corresponding to low loss EELS shown in e). Point EELS spectra were collected at the points marked. (b) EELS spectra collected at each of the points marked in (a). A greater lithium presence corresponds to thicker regions of the flake. (c) HAADF STEM image of a LiCoO₂. An EELS spectrum image was collected along the orange line and spectra from the points labeled A-H are shown in (d). (f) integrated EELS spectra across the line marked in (c).

Fig. 5 reveals the possibility of detecting lithium in 2-D materials having beam control in STEM mode (though the images were acquired before defocusing the beam). Examination of the Li K-edge for LiCoO_2 in Fig. 5(d) and (f) (marked with a red arrow) reveals a small peak at 56 eV, as well as the prominent signal at 62 eV, which indicates the presence of Li-ion. The pristine chemical environment can be preserved in STEM mode by defocusing the beam and using short acquisition times. The diameter of the beam was 10 nm in STEM mode (Fig. S11 Supporting information). The low loss EELS peak for the Li K-edge has a threshold at 54.8 eV and at 56 eV for elemental lithium. In other forms, such as LiOH , LiF , LiCl etc. it is observed that the lithium peak shifts towards higher binding energy at around 60 eV when it is bonded with some other elements [11].

2.3.1. CV measurements

So far, EELS measurements allowed lithium detection in different exfoliated materials. However, in this paper, the proposed Li detection technique is meant to be applied in materials for energy storage applications. Therefore, it is important to verify if the 2D flakes previously examined are electrochemically active and thus prove that the EELS technique is suitable for electrodes analysis. In order to do so, several electrodes of the active materials before and after exfoliation were prepared in order to assess their electrochemical properties and thus verify that the exfoliated materials still present electrochemical activity. Fig. 5 shows the cyclic voltammograms of these electrodes measured at 0.05 mV s^{-1} , in a half-cell configuration against Li foil, in 1 M LiPF_6 (1:1 EC/DMC).

In Fig. 6a and b reveal some differences between the exfoliated and the raw material. For the slurry broader peaks are observed, this may be an indication of overlapping of oxidation states and/or slower processes. The synthesis process of LiCoO_2 may also explain the shape of this voltammogram. For the exfoliated material, where the insertion/extraction process of Li^+ is improved due to shorter diffusion paths, the main intercalation peaks for LiCoO_2 at 3.89 V and 3.91 V are clearly observed [2]. To a lesser extent the same behaviour is observed for $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$. For LiMn_2O_4 , no major differences are observed after exfoliation, this may indicate that the material's electrochemical utilization at this scan rate is not optimized at nanoscale [17,27]. Further analysis of these results should be performed in the future. Nevertheless, this simple experiment clearly proves that after exfoliation, the exfoliated 2D flakes still present their typical electrochemical activities.

Figure 6 - Voltammograms for raw and exfoliated materials, obtained at 0.05 mV s^{-1} .

3. Conclusion

In this manuscript it was reported for the first time the probing of lithium in liquid phase exfoliated ultrathin 2D crystals using EELS. The spatial distribution and the electronic environment of lithium in 2-D materials was probed and the Li K-edge and the O K-edge were used to demonstrate the chemical bonding of the lithium to the transition metals. The peak broadening during absence of lithium and peak shift towards higher energy seen in lithiated compounds proves that lithium is still part of the structure even after exfoliation. However, the lithium is likely to have undergone localization defects. This is challenging as normally in STEM mode lithium is knocked out due to the electron beam interaction with the 2-D layered crystals making them highly sensitive to e-beam dose. The optimal dose and experimental conditions vary due to variations in flake thickness and the uncontrolled method by which the materials are exfoliated. This work furthermore shows the potential of liquid phase exfoliated materials as active materials for energy storage applications. However and more importantly, the identification and spatial distribution of lithium by EELS might open the possibility of testing other new and/or exotic intercalation materials, which present not well known properties.

4. Method

4.1. Exfoliation and physico chemical characterization of the 2D flakes

LiCoO₂, LiMn₂O₄ and Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ were exfoliated in a FisherBrand 11207 sonic bath. Initially, 2 mg mL⁻¹ suspensions were prepared in acetone, benzyl alcohol, benzyl benzoate, cyclohexanone, dibromomethane, N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF), isopropyl alcohol (IPA), N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and water. After 3 h under ultrasonic treatment at 37 kHz and 200 W power, the suspensions were centrifuged at 1500 rpm for one hour in a Heraeus Multifuge X1 Centrifuge. In order to estimate the quantity of the material dispersed the absorbance per cell length, A/l, of these dispersions was measured at 500 nm in a Varian, Cary 6000i UV-vis-NIR spectrometer. All measurements were performed in 10 mm matched quartz cuvettes. The solvents were then tested at different initial concentrations (5 mg mL⁻¹ and 10 mg mL⁻¹), different frequencies (37 kHz and 80 kHz) and times (6 and 9 h). The same optical measurements were repeated for these samples. All solvents used during exfoliation were sourced from Sigma Aldrich (99.99% purity) and used as purchased. The raw powders were purchased at Linyi Gelon LIB Co., Ltd. All chemicals were used as purchased. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed in a fully automated Bruker D5000 powder diffractometer equipped with a monochromatic Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda=0.15406$ nm) and a secondary monochromator. XRD patterns were collected between $10^\circ < \theta < 80^\circ$, with a step size of $2\theta=0.05^\circ$ and a count time of 12 s/step. All the samples were supported on a single crystal of silicon. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was performed in a Zeiss Ultra Plus microscope in high vacuum mode with an accelerating voltage of 5 keV.

4.2. Electrochemical studies

Slurries were prepared by mixing 80% of active material, 10% PVDF and 10% active carbon. In a normal procedure, proper amounts of active material and carbon additive were mixed very well in a mortar and added to a 4 mL solution of PVDF in NMP. After mixing for 24 h, the resulting slurries were pasted on 2.54 cm² copper (Li₄Ti₅O₁₂) and aluminium (LiCoO₂ and LiMn₂O₄) electrodes. The exfoliated materials were sprayed onto copper or aluminium electrodes in a USI Prism Ultracoat 300. Briefly, suspensions of electrochemically active material were fed into an automated pumping system that delivered the suspension at the tip of an ultrasonic spray head at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹. Ultrasonic vibrations disintegrated the liquid into small drops producing a mist that was propelled away from the spray-forming tip by a low pressure (69 kPa) air stream in the form of a spray cone. The mist was deposited onto substrates attached to a hot plate that maintained a temperature

suitable for the evaporation of the solvent. The spray head was moved at a constant spray height (35 mm) and speed (100 mm s^{-1}) by an automated gantry in x and y directions drawing a previously designed and specific spray pattern that produced a uniform film. Electrodes were assembled in a standard EL-CELL using lithium foil as counter electrode and lithium wire as reference. in 1 M LiPF_6 (1:1 EC/DMC). All the measurements were performed in a BioLogic VMP 300.

5. Microscopy analysis

For the electron microscopy studies material were dispersed in IPA, drop cast on TEM holey carbon Cu grid (400 mesh - Agar) and baked overnight in Precision Ion Polishing System (PIPS). The flakes were found to have a wide range of sizes (100 nm – 1 μm). EELS spectra were collected with a GIF Tridiem 863 EELS Spectrometer, Gatan, Inc. attached to a FEI TITAN field emission microscope operating at 300 kV. EELS spectra were obtained in TEM as well as in STEM mode. The energy dispersion was set as 0.1 eV/ch. The full width at half maximum of the zero loss peak in vacuum was 0.8–0.9 eV. The collection angle for the EELS spectra was 10 mrad with a convergence semi-angle of 21 mrad. Further experimental details in Supplementary information. The total beam current in TEM mode was 6.8 nA for a beam diameter of 100 nm and 150 nm (limiting electron dose to 86 and 38 C/cm^2 respectively). In STEM mode a 0.45 nA current and probe size of 1 nm was calculated to result in an electron dose of $2.8 \times 10^4 \text{ C}/\text{cm}^2$. No lithium signal was detected in STEM mode, due to this high electron dose. This resulted in no prominent lithium signal for LiMn_2O_4 (refer to Supplementary information). In order to minimize elemental loss and electron beam damage, the beam was defocussed to 1 μm (beam diameter of $\sim 10 \text{ nm}$ – Fig. S11) resulting in an electron dose under $600 \text{ C}/\text{cm}^2$. All STEM spectral analyses, besides imaging, were carried out using a defocussed beam, which limits spatial resolution but makes line and point EELS analyses feasible. The results are included in the Supplementary information.

X-ray photoemission spectroscopy analysis was carried out using an Omicron UHV XPS analysis system, with photoelectrons excited using a monochromated Al K α x-ray source ($h\nu=1486.6 \text{ eV}$) at a base pressure of $1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mbar}$. An electron energy analyser pass energy of 20 eV was used, yielding a combined instrumental resolution of $\sim 0.45 \text{ eV}$.

Author contribution

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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